

A Study on Mechanical Properties of Bamboo-Cotton Handloom Fabrics

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Abstract:

This paper aims to study mechanical properties of cotton-bamboo fabrics made on handloom using different blend ratio as well as weave structure. A single warp beam using 2/20 Ne cotton was made and various samples were prepared using 100% cotton, 50/50 (bamboo/cotton), and 100% bamboo yarn in weft direction. Samples were also prepared with 1/1 plain weave and 2/2 twill weave to see the impact of weave on mechanical properties of fabrics. Results indicate that as the bamboo contents increases in fabrics there is increase in tensile strength and tear strength due to higher strength of bamboo yarn. The Tearing strength of twill woven fabrics is more than plain woven fabrics due to higher float length of yarn. Bamboo blended fabrics exhibit lesser flexural rigidity than cotton fabrics. The crease recovery also increases with the increasing bamboo contents for all samples irrespective of plain and twill weave. The twill woven fabrics exhibit slightly higher crease recovery than corresponding plain woven fabrics. Results indicate that bamboo also help in improving abrasion resistance, which may be due to non-circular surface and striated cracks of bamboo fibres. The increase in bamboo contents in plain woven fabrics also improves pilling resistance as compared to twill woven fabrics. Use of bamboo fibres in handloom industry as eco-friendly fibres could be seen as promising scope for consumers and entrepreneurs who are environmental concerned.

Keywords: Blend, Cotton-Bamboo, Handloom, Mechanical Properties, Sustainability, Weave

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1. Introduction

Natural fibres are becoming popular for their unique properties like low density, excellent mechanical properties, durability, sustainability, and biodegradability [1]. Bamboo is a widely grown renewable material available in India which requires almost no care pesticides etc. that will decompose if discarded after the end-of-life naturally. Fibre extracted from bamboo would be environmentally friendly and a good option for sustainability [2]. Bamboo fibres may be classified into the natural bamboo fibre, bamboo pulp fibre, and bamboo charcoal fibre. Natural bamboo fibres are directly extracted from bamboo using physical or microbial degumming where crystalline structure of the original bamboo fibre does not change during the extraction process. Bamboo pulp fibre is made from bamboo pulp and bamboo charcoal fibre is made by surface treatment of nano-level bamboo charcoal powder, then slurry is added to the viscose and drawn into a wire shape [3, 4].

Figure 1: Bamboo Fibre: (a) macroscopic bamboo fibre (b) Scanning electron microscopic image [5]

The literature reveals that the bamboo fibre length ranges from 38 to 76 mm which is higher than cotton fibre (25–45 mm). Fibre fineness is coarser in bamboo (1.3 – 5.6 dtex) than cotton fibre (1.2 – 2.8 dtex). Fibre density of bamboo fibre (0.8–1.32 g/cc) is lower than cotton fibre (1.5 – 1.54 g/cc). Moisture regain of bamboo is generally 13 % which is higher than regain of cotton (8.5 %). Apart from it bamboo has more tensile strength than cotton [6–9].

The research reveals that the use of bamboo is gaining importance in clothing due to its sustainability factor and remarkable properties. It's fast growing plant with reduced water footprints as well as requires no pesticides and fertilisers. It has also lower carbon footprints as it absorbs CO₂ from atmosphere during its cultivation. Literature reveals that the bamboo is naturally antibacterial and has good moisture-wicking properties which assist in reducing bad odour and make the wearer comfortable [10, 11].

2. Experimental work

2.1 Materials and Method

A single warp beam using 2/20 Ne cotton was prepared and six samples were prepared using 100% cotton, 50/50 (bamboo/cotton), and 100% bamboo yarn in weft direction with 1/1 plain weave and 2/2 twill weave to see the impact of blend and weave on mechanical properties. The various properties were investigated as per ASTM/AATCC standards the briefing of which is as follows:

2.1.1 Tensile Strength

The ASTM D5304-95 (Strip test) standard was used to determine the tensile strength of the samples. The tensile strength of the fabric was evaluated using a universal testing machine in both directions i.e. warp and weft directions.

2.1.2 Tearing Strength

To evaluate the tearing strength of the samples, the ASTM D 1424:09 standard was implemented. Elmendorf tear tester was used to measure the tearing strength of all handloom samples. The specimen size was 7.5 cm × 10 cm and five tests were done both in warp and weft direction for each sample.

2.1.3 Bending & Flexural Rigidity

The testing method ASTM D1388-08 was used for the stiffness of the fabric. Bending length and flexural rigidity were measured using a Shirley Stiffness tester. The sample size was 6" x 1".

2.1.4 Crease Recovery Angle

The crease recovery of the fabric was carried out on the Crease recovery tester as per AATCC 66 standard. Crease recovery depends upon the construction, twist of yarn, pressure, and time. Six readings were taken in warp and weft direction each for all samples. A 500 gram load was applied for creasing for 5 minutes and the same time for recovery.

2.1.5 Abrasion Resistance

The abrasion-resistance test of the fabric was performed on the Martindale abrasion tester using the ASTM D4966 standard. Four specimens of each plain and twill woven fabric were taken to perform the test. The fabric samples were subjected to friction and rubbing against standard abrasive fabric during the test.

2.1.6 Pilling Resistant

The pilling resistance test of the fabric was performed on the Martindale abrasion and pilling tester as per ASTM D4970-02 standard. Four specimens of each plain and twill woven fabric were taken to perform the test. During the test, the fabric sample undergoes rubbing and abrasion against a standard abrasive fabric which simulates normal wear to generate pilling.

3. Result & Discussion

All handloom samples were conditioned in a testing atmosphere of 65 ± 2% RH at a temperature of 27 ± 2°C to ensure the reliability of the results. The following findings were obtained during the testing of handloom fabric samples.

Table 1: Fabric Specifications

Sample	Weave	Warp yarns	Weft yarns	EPI	PPI	GSM
S1	Plain	2/20 ^s Cotton	2/20 ^s Cotton	46	32	200
S2	Plain	2/20 ^s Cotton	2/20 ^s Bamboo/Cotton (50/50)	46	34	210
S3	Plain	2/20 ^s Cotton	2/20 ^s Bamboo	46	36	216
S4	Twill	2/20 ^s Cotton	2/20 ^s Cotton	46	46	237
S5	Twill	2/20 ^s Cotton	2/20 ^s Bamboo/Cotton (50/50)	46	48	248
S6	Twill	2/20 ^s Cotton	2/20 ^s Bamboo	46	50	256

Table 2: Mechanical Properties

S. ID.	Tensile strength (Kgf)		Tearing strength (Kgf)		Bending length (cm)		Flexural rigidity (mg.cm)		Crease recovery angle		Abrasion resistant (no. of cycles)	Pilling resistance Ratings
	WP*	WF	WP	WF	WP	WF	WP	WF	WP	WF		
S1	53.25	39.05	4.3	5.1	2	2.15	160	198.6	101	108	10,000	3
S2	48.6	42.85	4.9	5.6	1.95	1.95	155.6	155.6	106	110	11,000	4
S3	43.45	53.75	5	5.7	1.8	1.85	125.3	136.1	114	116	12,000	4
S4	56.1	55.7	6.1	6.2	2	2.05	189.6	203.8	105	108	12,000	2
S5	55.45	57.45	6.2	6.6	1.9	1.95	168.6	183.5	111	117	20,000	2
S6	44.55	86.85	6.7	7.1	1.75	1.85	135.7	161.3	121	124	26,000	3

*WP and WF refers testing in warp and weft direction respectively.

3.1 Tensile strength

Tensile strength of all samples was tested on Tensile Testing Machine, the result of which is shown in Table 2. Results indicate that as the bamboo content increases in weft direction, there is significant increase in tensile strength in weft direction. Same trends are observed for plain and twill woven. The results are supported by the findings that tensile strength of bamboo is higher than cotton [12]. The tensile strength in twill woven fabrics are higher than corresponding plain woven fabrics, the reason of which may be attributed to higher PPI for all twill woven samples. Another observation is that for all samples except S1 and S2, tensile strength for plain and twill woven fabric, the tensile strength in weft direction is higher than warp direction, which may be due to combined effect of higher bamboo content and PPI. Since the EPI is significantly higher than PPI resulting into higher tensile strength in warp wise than weft wise. S6 shows maximum tensile strength than all other samples which could be due to 100 % bamboo used in weft direction and maximum thread density.

Figure 2: Tensile strength

3.2 Tear strength

Tearing strength was measured on Elmendorf tear strength tester as per ASTM D1424 standard. The results are given in Table 2 & Fig. 3 which indicates that tear strength increases with increase in bamboo content which may be due to higher strength of bamboo yarn. The tearing strength in twill woven fabrics is higher than corresponding plain woven fabrics, which are due to higher float length of yarn. Another observation is that tearing strength of samples in weft direction is higher than in warp direction due to the use of bamboo in weft direction which offers more tearing resistance.

Figure 3: Tearing strength

3.3 Bending length & Flexural Rigidity

Results of bending length & flexural rigidity are shown in Table 2, Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. Bending length decreases with increase in bamboo content and as bending length is directly proportional to flexural rigidity which follows the same trend. The decrease in bending length is due to higher flexibility of bamboo yarn than cotton yarn. This may be due to higher crystalline structure of cotton fibre than bamboo yarn. However results are not significantly different in warp and weft direction as well as corresponding plain and twill woven fabrics.

Figure 4: Bending Length

Figure 5: Flexural Rigidity

a. Crease recovery

The results of crease recovery are shown in table 2 and Fig. 6 which indicates that the crease recovery increases with increasing bamboo content for all samples. Crease recovery is also slightly higher in weft direction than warp direction which is due to the combined effect of use of bamboo yarn in weft wise as well as lower thread density in weft direction. Another observation is that twill woven fabrics exhibit slightly higher crease recovery than corresponding plain woven fabric.

Figure 6: Crease Recovery Angle

b. Abrasion resistance

Abrasion resistance was measured on the Martindale abrasion tester, the results are shown in Table 2 and Fig. 7. A prominent observation about results reveals higher abrasion resistance of twill woven fabric than plain woven fabrics, the results of which seems to be contrary based on finding from literature review. Generally plain woven fabrics are more resistant to abrasion due to more interlacements and less exposed area than twill woven fabrics. A close look into results reveals that higher thread density in weft direction and resultant higher GSM has

resulted into higher abrasion resistance. Abrasion resistance also increases with the increase in bamboo content. The non-circular surface of bamboo fibres, along with striated cracks on the surface may contribute to its abrasion resistance. S3 and S6 samples exhibit higher abrasion resistance for plain woven and twill woven fabrics as 100 % bamboo yarn is used in weft direction.

Figure 7: Abrasion resistant

c. Pilling resistance

The pilling resistance was also measured on Martindale abrasion & pilling tester as per ASTM D4970-02 standard. The results are shown in Table 2 & Fig.8. Rating scale of pilling resistance is from 5 (best rating) to 1 (severe pilling). Result indicates that plain fabric is more resistant to pill formation than twill woven. This is due to more interlacement in plain woven fabrics which makes it less likely to pill. The increase of bamboo content in weft direction also gives more resistant to pilling.

Figure 8: Pilling Resistance

4. Conclusion

Bamboo is considered more environmentally friendly due to its lower water and pesticide usage in cultivation. The study reveals that the bamboo fibres showed greater influence on fabric mechanical properties and also shows desirable aesthetic properties. Usage of bamboo in clothing will increase its durability and will reduce flexural rigidity which gives more softness to the fabrics and hence increase the comfort to the wearer. Crease recovery as well as pilling resistance improves with the presence of bamboo fibre in fabrics. Tensile and tearing strength have shown greater improvement in bamboo blended fabric that cotton fabrics. Apart from enhancing mechanical, aesthetic properties, the bamboo is naturally antibacterial and has good moisture-wicking properties. Since consumers are getting environmentally aware, they are demanding sustainable and comfortable clothing especially in developed nations. It is expected that bamboo will gain importance in clothing due to its sustainability factor and remarkable properties.

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